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IRRIGATION POTENTIAL MAPPING USING GIS AND REMOTE SENSING DATA

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GEBA SUB BASIN

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1. Introduction

The regional SMIS project is highly working on the capacity development of professionals working in SSI schemes all over the region. As a continuation of its mission SMIS project has organized and financed a capacity development training in **Irrigation Potential Mapping Using GIS & Remote Sensing** in the regional state of Amhara since **July 4 through July 16, 2016** the training have covered all the steps and analyses starting from potential mapping that encompass the land suitability which is a function of soil, land cover and slope as well as availability of water resources at each outlet point of the watershed up to site selection and delineation of the possible command area of the proposed scheme.

Accordingly a team of experts from Tigray water Resource Bureau have got a chance to participate on the training organized by SMIS project. The Overall content of the training and practical exercises are summarized on this report.

2. Background

Giba Basin project areas for possible SSI schemes on the watershed is located as shown on the map on figure one, two and three figures covering seven weredas of the region and this sub basin is one of the tributaries to Tekeze river , and it is crucial for planning and management of water Resource projects in the sub basin.

Location Map of Giba Basin

Figure 1 Location Map of Giba Basin

Figure 2 Zoomed in location map of the watershed

3. Problem Description

Experience shows that many of water projects in the region have not planned properly, consequently the region has never optimized its financial resources, moreover projects have missed their first mission (Target), Hence we are pleased to break the existing trend of irrigation project planning and irrigation potential mapping studies have never carried out, yet

4. Description of the study

- Hydrological study (SWAT)
- Climate +Soil +Agronomy (Literature +GIS)
- Topography (TWI--GIS)
- Socio- economic , Need of farmers & Environmental

Figure 3 Project Area specific Location

5. General Objective

- **Irrigation potential mapping of Giba sub basin project area using ArcGIS and remote sensing.**

5.1 Specific Objectives

- **Scientific approach for Irrigation mapping of the study area**
 - **Water Demand (Determination)**
 - **Land Suitability (Mapping)**
 - **Water Resource Availability (Determination)**

(Identification of irrigation potential sites , planning and managing of irrigation projects) Specific Objectives

6. Expected Output & outcome

- **Irrigation potential mapping Vs all sources of uncertainty**
- **Great contribution to Higher officials, planners & Wereda ,Zone ,Regional bodies & the study will have an input to national Economic and planning purpose**

7. Research Gaps

Scarce availability of data set of Hydrological & meteorological data

- a. Soil map , land use map of the country**
- b. satellite imaged with high resolution**

8. Methodology

Figure 4 Topographic wetness Index(TWI)

Figure 5 Giba basin slope I n Radians

Figure 6 Giba basin TWI

Figure 7 Suitability land mapping and Interoperation

Figure 8 Giba basin slope classes

Figure 9 Giba basin slope and soil combination classes

Figure 10 Giba basin Land cover

Figure 11 Giba basin all suitability map for different slope combination

Figure 12 Giba basin suitability Map

- SUITABLE =102,228.2Ha (45.97%)
- NON-SUITABLE =118,995.85 Ha (54.03%)

9. Irrigation Requirement (GIR-Duty) and Seasonal water

- ET based on Solar Radiation, less subjected to local variations (Abteu, 1996), Checked with CropWAT-8 approach of Computing Eto.
- Eto-based on the most hot day in the year (Safest Side)
- Type of irrigation methods & Overall efficiency (Literatures)
- SWD is m^3/ha

- SWD of the study area(SWD*Land Suitability) in m^3

Figure 13 Solar Radiation Map

Figure 14 ETo mm/day Map

Figure 15 Monthly Rainfall in mm

Figure 16 Rain fall Isohytal map

Figure 17 Net demand mm/month =Montly (ETo-RF)

Figure 18 Gross irrigation Requirement (mm/month/ha)

Figure 19 Seasonal irrigation requirement (4 months Water Demand)

Figure 20 Seasonal water Demand (m³)

Over all water Demand in the project (899.04Mm³)

Figure 21 Overall water Demand in the basin

10. Water Availability Analysis

Surface water modeling using ArcSWAT i.e. GIS extension tool for hydrological modeling system

Data input in the model

- Geographical
- Meteorological/Climatological

Hydrological system

Figure 22 Projected DEM for Hydrological analyses using ARCSWAT modeling system

11. Results and Discussion

Model Index

$$r^2 = \frac{\left[\sum_{i=1}^n (q_{si} - \bar{q}_s)(q_{oi} - \bar{q}_o) \right]^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_{si} - \bar{q}_s)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (q_{oi} - \bar{q}_o)^2} \quad D = 100 \cdot \left[\frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n q_{si} - \sum_{i=1}^n q_{oi} \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^n q_{oi}} \right]$$

$$E_{NS} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_{oi} - q_{si})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_{oi} - \bar{q}_o)^2}$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Q_{sim,i} - Q_{obs,i})^2 \right]}$$

Figure 25 Some result table of each sub basin

Figure 26 SWATCHECK water balance summary result with no error message

Correlation Analyses

Figure 27 Correlation Analyses

Catchment Name	Volume Percentile Error(D)		RMSE		N _s		R ²	
	Daily	Monthly	Daily	Monthly	Daily	Monthly	Daily	Monthly
Outlet 45	-0.27		Calibration indexes		0.66		0.68	
			89					
Other outlet			Validation indexes					

Figure 28 Model simulation Result

Figure 29 Giba basin potential map

Figure 30 IDW availability

Figure 31 Suitability and Availability Map of Giba basin

Figure 32 Suitability, Availability and RF IYSHYAL map of Giba basin

Results & Discussions Remark

- From the **SWAT model** result still with some uncertainty the total minimal annual average water availability was tabulated to be **100,000lit/sec** and the duty of the area is tabulated as **1.7lit/sec/ha** and this can irrigate up to **58,823.53 ha** but we have a suitable land potential of **102,228.2 ha** as tabulated here only **59%** of the suitable land is irrigation potential

12. Conclusions & Recommendation

- How valuable is space born data in data poor environment
- GIS and remote sensing data plays a great role in preliminary irrigation potential identification and planning purpose
- Once we validate the data set to be used in GIS then it works fine and perfect b/s garbage in is garbage out and vise versa
- This work is done all in all at desk level therefore, this must be verified in the ground
- Since the basic obstacle of our works is data limitation so we professionals must work as hard as nail on data quality and the government should give a higher focus in alleviating this National Mess!!!
- Finally yet importantly the trainees would like to appreciate this start up work but still needs an advanced GIS and remote sensing trainings on the next phase of training taking this as the prerequisite for the next training that we propose.